

CO₂ Condensation and Sublimation on a Range of Substrates Under Simulated Mars Conditions

Supplementary Material: Keyence Measurements of Simulant Samples

1 Comparison between samples

2 Glass beads, 250-355 μm diameter, viewed at 50x zoom

66 grains marked (after removing 3 edge particles and effort to separate “connected” grains), including 3 amorphous/non-spherical beads.

- Contained 15 specks with diameter $<10 \mu\text{m}$ (removed as background dust or noise)
- Contained 2 more particles with diameter $<40 \mu\text{m}$ (removed as background dust)
- 49 particles used for this characterization

	Circle equivalent diameter [μm]	Max diam. [μm]	Min diam. [μm]	Circularity []	Area [μm^2]	Perimeter [μm]
Average	288.54	301.18	279.84	0.85	66077.62	987.82
Standard Deviation	29.62	40.22	30.79	0.06	12972.89	115.06
Max	348.34	449.99	331.39	0.91	95298.52	1344.08
Min	202.12	206.67	199.51	0.59	32085.19	694.66

Glass beads are very smooth. Here are images at 300x, 500x, and 1000x zoom – showing small pits and bumps scattered on a spherical bead.

3 Regolith simulant, <math><53 \mu\text{m}</math> diameter, viewed at 100x zoom

4334 grains marked (after manual removal of “smeared” areas that obviously did not contain accurate grain perimeters and effort to separate “connected” grains)

- Contained 3310 specks with diameter <math><10 \mu\text{m}</math> (removed as background dust or noise)
- 1024 particles used for this characterization

	Circle equivalent diameter [μm]	Max diam. [μm]	Min diam. [μm]	Circularity []	Area [μm^2]	Perimeter [μm]
Average	14.67	12.01	12	0.69	208.48	59.76
Standard Deviation	7.09	7.09	7.09	0.2	240.83	36.68
Max	50.37	48.21	48.21	1.11	1993.03	261.27
Min	5.55	2.05	2.05	0.14	24.2	23.56

The $<53\mu\text{m}$ grains are very angular and irregular in shape and size. Here are images at 500x and 1000x zoom.

4 Regolith simulant, 75-150 μm diameter, viewed at 50x zoom

5628 grains marked (after manual removal of “smear” areas that obviously did not contain accurate grain perimeters and effort to separate “connected” grains)

- Contained 2699 specks with maximum diameter $<10\ \mu\text{m}$ or minimum diameter $<2\ \mu\text{m}$ (removed as background dust or noise)
- 2929 particles used for this characterization

Circle equivalent diameter [μm]	Max diam. [μm]	Min diam. [μm]	Circularity []	Area [μm^2]	Perimeter [μm]
--	-----------------------------	-----------------------------	----------------	--------------------------	-----------------------------

Average	23.59	30.68	18.84	0.88	706.07	92.33
Standard Deviation	18.51	27.57	17.58	0.27	1524.8	100.53
Max	141.15	222.83	143.1	1.37	15647.87	1282.19
Min	7.11	10.5	2.1	0.07	39.69	22.74

The 75-150 μm grains are also angular and irregular in shape, but maybe more uniform and rounded than the smaller grains. The first row of images are at 200x zoom; the next 3 are at 400x zoom, with the color image showing the “height” of a few grains (as estimated by the Keyence, after doing the focus integration effort ... not sure how accurate it is so you probably shouldn't use it, but it does confirm that the heights of these grains is comparable to their planform dimensions; and the last four are of the largest grains in the 400x-zoom images, showing their texture and the smaller particles stuck to their sides.

5 Regolith simulant, 180-500 μm diameter, viewed at 50x zoom

681 grains marked (after effort to separate “connected” grains)

- Contained 251 specks with maximum diameter $<10 \mu\text{m}$ or minimum diameter $<2 \mu\text{m}$ (removed as background dust or noise)
- 430 particles used for this characterization

	Circle equivalent diameter [μm]	Max diam. [μm]	Min diam. [μm]	Circularity []	Area [μm^2]	Perimeter [μm]
Average	50.81	62.71	42.83	1.03	9478.52	186.81
Standard Deviation	97.4	125.23	86.41	0.22	29686.77	384.75
Max	495.83	665.87	444.53	1.36	193088.9	2018.97
Min	7.11	10.5	2.1	0.22	39.69	22.74

The 180-500 μm grains were harder to image together. Here are images of a single grain at 200x and 300x (same grain), and 200x zoom. These grains are angular, but appear more convex overall than the smaller grains (at the scale of the grain diameters – as in they wouldn’t fit as well together/pack well). They also are covered with very small dust particles.

